
EVALUATION OF SOURCE ROCK AND HYDROCARBON POTENTIALS OF WELL 11 MEREN OIL FIELD NIGER DELTA, NIGERIA

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Abstract

An evaluation of hydrocarbon generating potential of 11 fine grained sediments samples from well 11 in Meren oil field Niger Delta Basin using Rock Eval pyrolysis techniques and Total Organic Content (TOC) were carried out in this study. The well was investigated at depth interval range of 5160ft – 6030ft. The Total Organic Content (TOC) and Rock-Eval pyrolysis methods were used to measure organic matter contents and their thermal maturities in the source rocks respectively. Results of TOC values which ranges from 1.59 to 2.04wt% with the average value of 1.82wt% showed that the source rocks have good hydrocarbon yielding potential as it exceeded the minimum threshold for hydrocarbon yielding potential. The generating potential (GP) values (1.76mgHC/gTOC to 2.88mgHC/gTOC) indicated the source rock's ability to generate hydrocarbon. This also showed in the production index (PI) values which are above 1.0. Kerogen discrimination indicated the dominance of type III kerogen because of the low Hydrogen index (HI) values of 80.6 to 119.7mgHC/gTOC. This Kerogen type has the potential to produce more gas than oil. The cross plots of HI against OI, HI against Tmax and TOC against S2, confirmed the kerogen type to be Type III. The Vitrinite reflectance (Ro) values which ranged from 0.51% to 0.58% and the Maximum Temperature (Tmax) released during pyrolysis with values ranging from 426 °C to 430 °C indicate early mature source rocks.

Keywords: Source Rocks - Agbada Formation · Niger Delta · Hydrocarbon Potential · Total Organic Carbon · Rock-Eval.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important element of a petroleum system is the source-rock, which holds a statutory relevance in the entire history of hydrocarbon formation. Source rocks are very fine-grained organic-rich sedimentary rocks that are capable of producing hydrocarbon when subjected to high temperature and or pressure. Simply put, Source rock can be seen as a part, or component of the petroleum system composed of an efficient quantity of organic matter sufficient enough to yield and let-out hydrocarbon upon maturity. Hence, there is almost no petroleum system without a petroleum source rock presence, that holds the obligation of hydrocarbon generation.

According to Carol, (1999) a rock is qualified as a source rock if it has the capacity to yield or has yielded dischargeable quantities of hydrocarbon. Hence, considering the role of the source rock in a petroleum system it can therefore, be established that the quantity, quality, and type of hydrocarbon is directly proportional to the source rock composition and as such the conventional rule of source rock exploration holds that when a source rock has been identified, the quality must also be characterized in order to derisk uncertainties that may cloud expectations and estimations. Three very important factors and two vital processes have been outlined as components which qualify a source rock include: organic matter quality, and quantity, and thermal maturity (Peters and Cassa, 1994), while the processes which influence the factors include; the depositional settings and disposition, structural and tectonic history of the area. The depositional setting and disposition influence the organic matter quantity and quality, while the structural and tectonic setting account of the area influence the thermal maturity (Filipo, Schamel, Monthioux, 1999).

Evaluation of the organic matter quantity is resolved through the assessment of the TOC present in the source-rock while quality is assessed by substantiating and exerting present kerogen type in the source-rock and thermal maturity estimated using vitrinite reflectance analysis respectively.

The geochemistry of sedimentary rocks is vital to deduce factors that control sediment characteristics during and after their deposition and also to describe the relationship between specific units of both clastic and carbonate strata (Nagarajan Madhavaraju, Nagendra, 2007; Madhavaraju and Lee 2009). The significance of geochemistry in describing the origin of sedimentary rocks, paleo-weathering conditions as well as tectonic evolutions of sedimentary basins is recognized in many studies (Cullers, Graf, 1988; Nagarajan, Madhavaraju, Nagendra 2007; Frimmel 2009). Organic geochemical analyses are unique in determining the hydrocarbon potential of sedimentary rocks as well as playing a pivotal role in the continued development of oil and gas exploration and production (Philp 2014). These analyses have been a significant tool in determining the hydrocarbon prospectivity of the Niger Delta. Several studies have been conducted within the Niger Delta area, especially in the area of source rock geochemistry. Among them: the influence of origin, depositional environment and thermal maturity of organic matter on the occurrence of aromatic hydrocarbons in source rocks from the central and northwestern Niger Delta was investigated by Akinlua, Ajayi, Jarvie, Adeleke (2019).

The type and the thermal maturity of organic matter and their depositional environment have significant effects on the concentration of trace elements in source rocks (Lewan, 1984). Metals of proven association with organic matter may be used as reliable correlation tools. Nickel, vanadium, and cobalt (usually referred to as biophile elements) are such examples (Barwise, 1990; Udo, Ekwere, Abrakasa 1992; Akinlua Ajayi, Jarvie, Adeleke, 2008). The geochemical characteristic and intrinsic distribution of rare earth elements in geological

formation would make them useful geochemical tools to determine the origin, depositional environment, and thermal maturation of organic matter (Henderson, 1984; Takeda & Arikawa, 2005; Akinlua *et al.*, 2008).

Geologic Setting

The study area is located within the Niger Delta, Nigeria. The Niger Delta sedimentary basin is a product of triple junction phenomenon comprising the Gulf of Guinea, South Atlantic Ocean and Benue depression. The Niger delta is one of the world's largest tertiary delta system and an extremely prolific hydrocarbon province. The Niger Delta is situated on the Gulf of Guinea on the west coast of central Africa and extends throughout the Niger Delta Province as defined by Klett *et al.*, (1997). It occupies an area of about 75,000 km² with clastic sequence which reaches a maximum thickness of 9000-12000m of sediment and a total sediment volume of 500,000km³ (Sonibare *et al.*, 2008) and a sediment thickness of over 10 km in the basin's depocenter (Kaplan *et al.*, 1994) between latitude 3°N and 6°N and longitudes 5°E and 8°E. Stratigraphically, the thick sedimentary sequence is made up of three lithostratigraphic units namely; the Benin, Agbada and Akata Formations (Fig 1). The three formations exist in the subsurface of the onshore and offshore of Niger Delta (Frankl and Cordry, 1967; Weber Daukoru, 1975; Knox and Omatsola, 1989; Obaje and Okosun, 2013; Short and Stauble, 1967).

Fig 1. Regional Stratigraphy of the Niger Delta Showing Different Formations (after Ozumba, 2013)

The Niger Delta Basin stratigraphy shows a typical off-lap sequence broadly divided into three main chronostratigraphic units (Reijers, 2011) as stated above, comprising time equivalent proximal-to-distal prograding facies. These units comprise the:

- ❖ Akata Formation which occurs as the bottom set and consists of over 90% prodelta marine shale and less than 10% of sandstone (Short and Stauble, 1967). The associated sandstone units are generally low stand turbidite fans deposited in a deep marine setting (Reijers, 2011). Its thickness ranges from 600m to 6000m, while its age ranges from Eocene to Recent. This is the basal marine shale, 600 – 6000m (1969 – 19688ft) thick. These pro-delta shales are medium to dark gray, medium hard, at places soft, gumbo like, and sandy or salty. The shales are under-compacted and may contain lenses of abnormally high-pressured siltstone or fine-grained sandstone (Short and Stauble, 1967). According to Doust and Omatsola (1990), the Akata shales contain a few streaks of sand, possibly turbiditic in origin and were deposited in holomarine (delta front to deeper marine) environments.
- ❖ The Agbada Formation represents the foreset of the Niger Delta comprised of delta front lithofacies consisting mostly shoreface and channel sand deposits with minor shale in the upper parts and an alternation of sand and shale of almost equal proportion in the lower part. Its thickness ranges from about 3000m to 4500m. The Agbada Formation is overlain by a paralic sequence of inter-bedded sand and shales, 300 – 4500m (984 – 14766ft) thick, which is termed the Agbada Formation. It consists of sandstones and shales of deltaic front, distributary's channel and deltaic plain origin. The sandstones are medium to fine grained, the shales are medium to dark gray, fairly hard, and silty. At the central part of the delta, the formation attains a maximum thickness of 3,940m (12,000ft) and thins northward and toward the north western and eastern flanks of the delta (Short and Stauble, 1967; Avbovbo, 1978)
- ❖ The Benin Formation is an upper delta plain lithofacies that consists of over 90% massive continental sands and gravels with clay intercalations (Short and Stauble, 1967). It has variable thickness, which generally exceed 2100m and ranges in age from Oligocene – Recent (Whiteman, 1982). The topmost unit, which consists of fluvial gravels and sand occurring from the contemporary delta surface to a depth of about 2134m (7,000ft), is called the Benin formation. It consists predominantly of massive, highly porous, fresh water bearing sandstones, with local thin shale inter beds, which are considered to be of braided stream origin. Mineralogically, the sandstones consist dominantly of quartz and potash feldspar and minor amounts of plagioclase (Frankl and Cordry, 1967; Short and Stauble, 1967; Burke *et al.*, 1972; Weber and Daukoru, 1975).

Materials and Methods

Source rock samples were collected at different depths from the oil field (Meren field) in the paralic sequence of Agbada Formation, northwestern Niger Delta. The unwashed ditch-cutting samples will be initially rinsed to remove drilling mud and then dried at room temperature for 24 hours to avoid agglomeration or clumps of the samples at some point in crushing. The ditch cutting samples will be crushed to the size of 250 μ m, with the aim of reducing the particles to expose more sample material to chemical processing and to completely separate all organic constituents.

Geochemical Approach: 11 samples collected at different depths from well 11 in Meren field were investigated by running Rock Eval pyrolysis and Total Organic Content (TOC). The well was investigated at depth interval range of 5160ft – 6030ft.

Total Organic Content (TOC) Analysis

In determining the Total organic carbon (TOC) (% C), an ELTRA CS800 Carbon and Sulphur Determinator (catalyst) was used as a step to discriminating potential source and non-source rock, since it is expected that finer grained facies have greater TOC potential (Hunt, 1996; Huc, 1988). Generally, the lower TOC limit for effective shale to generate hydrocarbon is 0.5 wt. % and for carbonate source rock is 0.3% wt. respectively (Hunt, 1979). Initial samples preparation involved the pulverization of all samples selected for analysis, using an automated rock pulverizer. The pulverized samples were then sieved through a 25 µm sieve and then 0.1g of each sample was weighed out (against a standard: 0.1015 – 0.0985gm) and processed for TOC analysis. Prepared samples were fed into the TOC analyzer (LECO) and analyzed for fifty seconds each. Tissot and Welte (1984) had shown that a linear proportionality exists between the quantity of oil generated in any given volume of source rock and its organic carbon content were obtained.

A constant weight (20g) of each composited sample was initially given a hot (5%) Hydrochloric acid treatment to remove carbonates prior to complete digestion in 60% Hydrofluoric acid (HF) in a fume cupboard. Gentle agitation of the acid and sample mixture was carried out to aid acid digestion. Distilled water was added several times to wash off traces of the HF. The samples were decanted before they were further given a hot (10%) Hydrochloric acid (HCl).

Rock-Eval Pyrolysis

The main objective of Rock-Eval analysis involves the pyrolysis samples up to 550°C in order to extract hard geochemical data for source rock evaluation. This method of source rock maturity evaluation (Espitalie *et al.*, 1977), involves passing a stream of helium through 100mg sample that has been initially heated to 300°C, and programmed to rise at about 25°C/min, up to 550°C. 100g of each pulverized sample was sieved through a 25µm mesh screen. The weight of each sample required for analysis, (TOC dependent) was weighed and analyzed, in the course of this work.

The hydrocarbon generation potentials, maturity, quantity/quality of kerogen were determined using a Rock-Eval Pyrolyser instrument of the Chaliton Laboratories Limited, Lekki Lagos.

Rock-Eval pyrolyser is one of the most important and least complicated methods of analyzing live organic carbon. Ramachandra *et al.*, (2012) states that the sample with TOC values greater than 0.5% for shale and 0.3% for carbonates are appropriate for Rock-Eval pyrolysis. Rock eval pyrolysis technique has been used to determine the petroleum potential and the thermal maturity of kerogen occurring in the sample (Barker, 1974; Espitalie, 1986)

The rock eval parameters obtained from pyrolysis using rock eval are furnished in Table 1. both measured (S1, S2, S3 and Tmax) and calculated parameters (OI, HI, PI, GP, Ro etc) from Rock Eval pyrolysis help in the determination of kerogen type, hydrocarbon generation efficiency and maturation.

Rock-Eval pyrolysis determines OM quality and thermal maturity. This procedure includes measurements of free hydrocarbons (HC) that can be vaporized without cracking kerogen of the rock (peak S1, mg HC/g rock), hydrocarbons derived from cracking of kerogen (peak S2, mg HC/g rock), organic carbon dioxide (peak S3, mgCO₂ /g rock) and a temperature at which the S2 peak reaches its maximum (Tmax, oC). Based on these measurements, production index $PI = S1/(S1+S2)$, hydrogen index $HI = (S2/TOC) * 100$ (mg HC/g TOC), S2/S3 ratio and oxygen index $OI = (S3/TOC) * 100$ (mg CO₂/g TOC) were calculated.

Calculated Vitrinite Reflectance

In determining the calculated vitrinite reflectance value of each sample that was geochemically tested, the Javie et al. (2001) formula was adopted and used with caution to convert Rock-Eval pyrolysis T to vitrinite max reflectance (R): $R_o(\text{Calculated}) = (0.0180)(T_{\text{max}}) - 7.16$. According to Javie et al. (2001), the application of the formula works well for low-sulfur types II and III shales, but is not recommended for very low or high maturity rocks ($T < 420^\circ\text{C}$ or $> 500^\circ\text{C}$). It is not also max recommended when S is < 0.50 mg HC/g rock.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the organic carbon richness and Rock-Eval pyrolysis of the well is presented in Table 1. The sediments of well 11 of Meren field contains the total organic content (TOC) of 1.59-2.04wt% with the average value of 1.82wt%, this shows that the field contain moderate to high organic matter which signify good hydrocarbon generative potential. Since the average is above 0.5wt% minimum threshold for hydrocarbon generating potential, it can therefore be rated as good source rock and this is in agreement with the work of Nordeng, 2013 which explains that source rock with TOC value of less than 0.5wt% have poor hydrocarbon generating potentials, between 0.5 to 1.0wt% have fair to good hydrocarbon generating potential, between 2.0 to 4.0wt% have good to very good hydrocarbon generating potentials and lastly above 4.0wt% have very good to excellent hydrocarbon generating potentials.

The vitrinite reflectance calculated from the field with the value of 0.51 and 0.58% and the average 0.55% is an indication of immature to marginal maturity of source rocks which agrees with the work of Cardott, 2016, which stipulates that source rocks with R_o values less than 0.55% and above 0.55% are immature and mature respectively. The cross plot of Depth versus Vitrinite Reflectance also confirms it which is in alignment with the work of Petters, 1986 which stipulates that organic matter are immature when T_{max} has value less than 434°C and PI values less than 0.2mgHC/gTOC and oil generating from source rocks begins at T_{max} of 435 to 465°C and PI values between 0.2 and 0.4mgHC/gTOC, and gas generation from source rock begins at T_{max} 470°C and PI values above 0.4mgHC/gTOC.

The organic matter type is the Type III kerogen which is equivalent to "Gas Prone". The hydrogen index (HI) and oxygen index (OI) with the values 80.6 to 120.3mgHC/gTOC and 75.5 to 92.6mgCO₂/gTOC respectively indicates greater potentials to generate gaseous hydrocarbon of which the cross plots of HI and OI confirms it, it also aligns with the work of Tissot and Welte, 1984; Petters and Cassa, 1994 which stipulate that organic matter with HI values > 600 mgHC/gTOC and OI values > 50 CO₂/gTOC is OF Type I kerogen, also HI values of 300-600mg HC/gTOC and OI value < 50 mgCO₂/gTOC is of Type II kerogen while a low HI values of 200-300mgHC/gTOC is a mixture of Type II and Type III kerogen. HI value of 50-200mgHC/gTOC and OI values of 50-200 mgCO₂/gTOC are of Type III and lastly HI values < 50 mgHC/gTOC are indication of Type IV kerogen. The low HI values also signify terrestrial origin and it is in agreement with the work of Nwachukwu 1984. Similarly, low S₂ values indicate 'Gas Prone' kerogen.

Comparatively, the GP (Generation Potentials) values 1.76-2.88mgHC/gTOC whose average value is 2.32mgHC/gTOC indicates fair to good source rock generative potentials with the maximum values falling within the lower Agbada Formation. The productive index (PI) values of (0.11 to 0.23mgHC/gTOC) also indicates fair to good source rock potentials and these values aligns with the work of Hunt, 1995 which explains that source rock with GP values less the 0.2mgHC/gTOC is poor, between 0.2 to 2.5mgHC/gTOC, is fair and good when the generating potential is above 5mgHC/gTOC.

The study shows two lithostratigraphic units, the Benin Formation which consists of massive fine to medium grained sandstones with thin-bedded siltstones and shale, and the Agbada Formation which consists of alternating shale/mudstones and sandstones with siltstones. This agrees with the work of Obaje and Okosun, 2013.

Table 1: TOC and Rock Eval Pyrolysis for Well 11 of the Meren 69 Field

S/N	Depth (ft)	Sample type	LECO TOC	S1	S2	S3	Tmax	R _o	HI	OI	S2/S3	S1/TOC	S1+S2	PI
1	5160	Cuttings	1.59	0.46	1.42	1.49	426	0.51	89.3	93.7	1.0	3.0	1.94	0.23
2	5280	Cuttings	1.49	0.46	2.10	1.50	428	0.54	108.2	77.3	1.4	2.0	2.6	0.17
3	5370	Cuttings	1.82	0.29	2.18	1.72	429	0.56	119.7	94.5	1.3	2.0	2.5	0.12
4	5460	Cuttings	1.79	0.47	1.73	1.45	429	0.56	96.6	81.0	1.2	3.0	2.2	0.21
5	5520	Cuttings	1.68	0.39	1.54	1.29	427	0.53	91.7	76.8	1.2	2.0	1.93	0.20
6	5580	Cuttings	1.83	0.27	1.49	1.64	426	0.51	81.4	89.6	0.9	1.0	1.76	0.15
7	5670	Cuttings	2.02	0.45	2.43	1.52	428	0.55	120.3	75.2	1.6	2.0	2.88	0.16
8	5760	Cuttings	1.75	0.22	1.83	1.62	430	0.58	104.6	92.6	1.1	1.0	2.1	0.11
9	5920	Cuttings	2.04	0.41	1.80	1.54	428	0.54	80.6	77.6	1.0	2.0	2.04	0.21
10	5970	Cuttings	1.75	0.38	1.64	1.61	427	0.53	93.7	92	0.53	2.0	2.02	0.17
11	6030	Cuttings	2.01	0.42	1.62	1.56	428	0.54	88.2	75.5	0.54	2.0	2.21	0.22

Table 1: Shows the total organic content (TOC) values Rock Eval generated parameters (S1, S, S3 and Tmax) Calculated parameters (OI, HI, PI, GP, R_o)

Where **TOC** (wt%) is the Total Organic Content which is the organic carbon richness of the samples

S1 is the thermos vaporized free hydrocarbons mgHC/grock

S2 is the pyrolysis hydrocarbon from cracking of organic matter mgHC/grock

S3 is the amount carbon di-oxide (CO₂) released through heating the organic matter.

Tmax (%) is the highest temperature for generating a maximum amount of hydrocarbon during pyrolysis.

R_o (calculated vitrinite reflectance) is expressed as $0.018(T_{max}) - 7.16$ measured in %

HI (hydrocarbon index or hydrocarbon potential) is a parameter used to characterize the origin of organic matter. It is expressed as $100 \times S2 / TOC$ mgHC/gTOC.

OI (oxygen index) is expressed as $100 \times S3 / TOC$ mgCO₂/gTOC

GP (generating potential) is expressed as $S1 + S2$ mgHC/gTOC.

PI (production/transformation index) is used to characterize the evolution level of the organic matter. It is expressed as $S1 / (S2 + S3)$ mgHC/gTOC

Fig. 2: Cross Plots of Generation Potential (GP) versus Total Organic Matter (TOC) (Modified after Hunts, 1995)

Fig. 3: Cross Plot of S2 Versus TOC (Modified after Hunt, 1995), Grosjean, Hall and Boreham (2017).

Quality of Organic Matter (Kerogen Type Determination)

One of the most common methods of classifying the quality of organic matter is by using a modified Van Krevelen, or HI vs. OI, diagram (Tissot *et al.*, 1974). In this plot three main types of kerogen (insoluble, non-extractable organic matter) are shown (Tissot and Welte, 1984). Type I is a sapropelic (algal) and very oil prone kerogen. It originates mainly from

lacustrine algae. Type II kerogens are oil prone and the most common for petroleum source rocks. It is a lipid-rich type of kerogen and its major contributors are phyto- and zooplankton marine organisms. Type III is a humic and gas-prone type of kerogen and represents terrigenous organic matter. Type II/III is transitional between types II and III. Inert kerogen is typically referred to as type IV and would plot near the bottom of a modified van Krevelen diagram (Demaison *et al.*, 1983).

The quality of organic matter can be differentiated from the HI and OI values. HI is mathematically expressed as $(100 \times S_3) / \text{TOC}$ (Hunt 1995; Tissot and Welte, 1984; Peters and Cassa 1994).

Fig 4; shows the hydrogen index of the studied samples with hydrogen index (HI) ranging from 81.4-120.3mgHC/gTOC which fell within type III kerogen and have greater potential to generate gaseous hydrocarbon. Also, the oxygen index (OI) of the studied samples range from 75.5 to 94.5mgCO₂ which also indicate gas prone. The curved lines demarcate the zones for the different kerogen types. All plotted samples fell within the type III zone.

Fig. 4: Modified Van Krevelene Diagram indicating the Kerogen Type III Organic Matter

Thermal maturity of organic matter

The main indices for thermal maturity are Tmax and Production index PI and HI

Tmax is measured at maximum S₂ generation and mostly depends on time/temperature condition and organic matter type (it is a maturity parameter)

Fig. 5: Cross Plot of Hydrogen Index (HI) Versus Tmax (Modified after Espitalie, Depth Versus Hydrocarbon (Kerogen type III) Generation.

CONCLUSION

The well 11 of the Meren field has more gas potentials than oil because it belongs to the Type III kerogen. The gas can be termed “Early dry gas” because most of the samples have Vitrinite Reflectance (Ro) values less than 0.55%.

The combined use of rock-Eval Pyrolysis and Total Organic Content analysis shows that the shales of the well 11 have a good tendency to yield hydrocarbon even though it has more gas than oil as all the plotted points fell within the type III kerogen.

Early maturity of shales of well 11 started at depth 5370ft with vitrinite reflectance of 0.51% (top oil window) and actual maturity of the shales began at depth 5970ft with vitrinite reflectance of 0.58%, Tmax value of 430% and thermal alteration index value (TAI) of 3. At this depth, “waxy oil” can be noticed though not in commercial quantity due to the presence of waxy materials. (ie plant cuticles from higher plants-terrestrial materials).

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